

A global expert assessment on the role of honeybee colony acoustics associated with apiary monitoring and some ecological factors

(Note: This questionnaire is promoted by a PhD student and team working on honeybee acoustics at Hefei Institutes of Physical Science (HFIPS), Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), University of Science and Technology of China (USTC). The main objective of this questionnaire is to gather information (from experts) for assessment of the role of honeybee colony acoustics in relation to monitoring apiaries, ecological and other factors. It is promised that your personal information would be kept confidential. Moreover, your other responses will be used only for research purpose and be published in such a way that you will remain anonymous and impossible to trace).

* Required

1. Email *

Personal Data

2. Question#1: Your Name

3. Question#2: Email address

4. Question# 3- Age *

Mark only one oval.

< 20

20-35

36-50

51-65

66-80

> 80

5. Question#4- Sex/Gender *

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

6. Question#5- Please provide your country name, location/address of work along with coordinates so that the geographical coordinates of your location appear on the map. *

7. Question#6 – Education *

Mark only one oval.

- PhD
- Master
- Undergraduate
- Researcher
- Other: _____

8. Question#7 – Employment *

Mark only one oval.

- Researcher / Professor
- Student
- Retired
- Unemployed
- Other: _____

9. Question#8: In relation to which factor (s) you works on bee's acoustics? *

Check all that apply.

- Colony health
- Swarming
- Pests and pathogens
- Predator attacks
- Pesticides
- Weather condition (Temperature, Humidity)
- Environmental pollution
- Land cover
- Land management
- Food availability
- Spatiotemporal patterns

Other: _____

Research Question:
Questions relating to the
role/importance of
honeybee colony
acoustics associated with
apiary monitoring and
some ecological factors

Below, please select one option out of 5 point scale where 1= Not important, 2= A little important, 3= Important, 4= Very important, 5= The most important. You can also select the option of "Unknown" if you think there is no sufficient evidence to make a judgment on whether or not the impact is happening or likely to happen.

11. Question# 2: Please select below the confidence score (1-3) for each factor which can be effectively monitored through honeybee colony acoustics. Note that score 1= Low confidence, 2= Medium confidence, 3= High confidence. You can also select the option of “Unknown” if you think there is no sufficient evidence to make a judgment on whether or not the impact is happening or likely to happen. *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1) Low	2) Medium	3) High	Unknown
Colony health	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Swarming	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pests and pathogens	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Predators attack	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pesticides	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Weather (Temperature, humidity)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Environmental pollution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Land cover	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Land management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food availability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Spatiotemporal patterns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. Question# 3: Please write comments below on the importance of factors (colony health, swarming, pests and pathogens, predators, pesticides, weather conditions, environmental pollution, land cover, land management, food availability, spatiotemporal patterns) in perspective of their monitoring via honeybee colony acoustics. Where applicable, please provide proper reference. You can preferably comment only the factor (s) in which you have more expertise, and left others unanswered for which you are not expert. *

13. Question#4: What do you suggest are the new areas where honeybee colony acoustics could be used to monitor them? If possible, please shortly describe how can colony sound be used (which sound features)? *

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Forms